

Comparative Studies on the Effects of High Sound Levels on the Haematological Parameters and Antioxidant Levels of Wistar Albino Rats

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ABSTRACT

The study comparatively evaluates the effects of high sound level from a generator set on haematological and antioxidant factors using albino rats of the Wistar strain. Fifty (50) Wistar albino rats of known weight were acclimatized for 14 days and divided into 3 main groups, which includes a control group, group 1 and group 2. Group 1 (for high sound level of 85db -105db) and group 2 (for low sound level of 40db - 55db) were sub divided into subgroups of five albino rats each and exposed to way off fumes from electrical generator sounds at different sound level for 8 hours each day for 28days. The result in group 1 at that high sound level shows an adverse effect on the body immune defense system as the concentrations of the antioxidant enzymes glutathione peroxidase, catalase and glutathione increased significantly ($p<0.05$) when compared to group 2 and the control group. There was an increase in the concentrations of malondialdehyde, and hematological parameters (RBC, WBC, PCV, heamaglobin, platelets) when compared to the control group and group 2. This shows that high noise pollution from the generator set can cause adverse effects to the body immune defense system.

Keywords: High Sound; Haematological Parameters; Antioxidant and Albino Rats

INTRODUCTION

Noise is a common physical nonspecific stressor and its physiological response as a stressor is the same as any other nonspecific physical stressor ^[1] noise affects the normal functioning of the cardiovascular, endocrine, and immune systems in the body as they manage to balance with the environmental or perceived demands of the individual. This results to an imbalance between the demand and the individual's resources to adapt which determines the individual's ability to deal with noise-induced stress ^[2]. Therefore, the body's inability to handle any overstimulation can result to hazardous stress implications which can affect the immunity and hence causing disease state (Basner and Samel, 2005). Noise stress may lead to noise-induced hearing loss by causing changes in the cell-mediated immune response (Basner and Samel, 2005). This noise stress can also result to sleep

deprivation because of its effect on the immune function and also this immune suppression from the stress load can increase the risk of acquiring diseases.

Many people are exposed to hazardous noise levels from work environment, urban traffic, or household appliances, etc., which affects their general health and lifestyle. In a particular industrious layout in Aba-north local government area of Abia state, where the noise level is high between 65 decibels to 95 decibels and above, the population which includes traders, transporters, club houses, tailors and many mini production workshops depend on their noisy generators to run their industrial machines and other electrical appliances. These independent workshops run generator which is their main source of power for over 8 hours on the average every day to power their heavy machines and electrical appliances, the generators are not soundproof and also emits poisonous fumes from its combustion of gasoline. Also, the generators are kept very close to their worktable and machine as they have very limited space which exposes them very closely to the hazardous health challenges from the noisy generator and its poisonous fumes. The environment is densely populated during the day due to activities of hundreds of production workshops, thousands of traders in that area and also noisy activities of motorist passing by.

Cellular activities produce reactive oxygen species which are scavenged by enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidants in order to prevent oxidative stress^[3]. Oxidative stress is generated by an imbalance in the amount of free radicals produced and the antioxidant system of the body^[3]. Antioxidants can decrease the cellular population of reacting oxygen species either by increasing the activities of the antioxidant enzymes (like catalase, superoxide dismutase and glutathione peroxidase) or by stopping the activities of ROS- generating enzymes like NAD(P)H oxidase and xanthine oxidase (XO)^[3]. Elevated concentrations of the antioxidant enzymes during prolonged noise stress can cause a lot of immune dysfunctions, resulting to serious health challenges.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

List of chemicals/reagents used

All the chemicals used in this study were of analytical grades and products.

Table 1: List of chemicals and reagents and their manufacturers.

Reagents/ Chemicals	Manufacturer
Buffer	Randox Kit, UK
Phosphate buffer	Randox Kit, UK
α – oxoglutarate	Randox Kit, UK
2, 4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine	Randox Kit, UK
Carbonate buffer pH	Randox Kit, UK
Xanthine oxide 0.3 μ /ml	Randox Kit, UK
Sodium hydroxide solution	Randox Kit, UK
2-Amino, 2-methly-1-propanol pH 11 (7.9 M)	Randox Kit, UK

Na ₂ PO ₄ (80 nM)	Randox Kit, UK
ethylene diamine tetra acetate (EDTA)	Drug House (BDH) Ltd
Tris-HCl	Drug House (BDH) Ltd

Experimental Animals

Fifty (50) albino rats of the Wistar strain aged 10-12 weeks and weighing 70 -100g bred in animal house of the Department of Zoology and Environmental Biology (ZEB), University of Nigeria, Nsukka Enugu State were used for this study. The animals were transported in aluminium cages to Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike. All animals were housed at controlled room temperature of about 27-30°C with a photoperiod of 12-hour light and 12-hour dark per day. The animals were fed Vital Growers Mash and water ad libitum and allowed to acclimatize to their environment for 7 days before experimentation.

Toxicological Study Design

The fifty (50) albino rats of the Wistar strain aged 10 - 12 weeks and weighing 70 -100 g bred were all fed with Vital growers' mash and water, then were randomly grouped into 3 main groups, which consist of a control group, group 1 and group 2. Group 1 (for high sound level of 85db - 105db) and group 2 (low sound level of 40db - 55db) were sub divided into subgroups with five albino rats and exposed to way off fume from electrical generator sounds at different noise levels for 8 hours each day for 28days as follows;

Control group: kept away from generator set at noise level less than 30 decibels

Group 1a: Exposed to noise level of 85 decibels

Group 1b: Exposed to noise level of 95 decibels

Group 1c: Exposed to noise level of 105 decibels

Group 1d: Exposed to noise level of above 105 decibels

Group 2a: Exposed to noise level of 55 decibels

Group 2b: Exposed to noise level of 50 decibels

Group 2c: Exposed to noise level of 45 decibels

Group 2d: Exposed to noise level of 40 decibels

Group 2e: Exposed to noise level of below 40 decibels

They were anaesthetized with chloroform, sacrificed by cervical dislocation and blood samples collected through cardiac puncture using 2ml syringes. Blood samples for biochemical assays were collected in plain tubes and allowed to clot before centrifugation and the sera were separated thereafter and used for the assays, while the blood samples for haematological parameters were collected in EDTA-containing sample bottles and used for the tests.

Determination of MDA Concentration

The concentration of malondialdehyde (MDA) was evaluated in the serum. The method described by Wallin was used. The principle of the method was based on the spectrophotometric measurement of the colour developed

during the reaction of thiobarbituric acid with MDA. The solutions were cooled under tap water and the absorbance was measured with an ultraviolet (UV) spectrophotometer (T80+ UV/Visible Spectrophotometer, PG Instruments Ltd., Leicestershire, United Kingdom) at 532 nm. The concentration of MDA in the samples was calculated by using the absorbance coefficient, MDA-TBA complex $1.56 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-1} \cdot \text{M}^{-1}$.

Assays of the Activities of Serum Antioxidant Enzymes

Superoxide dismutase activity was assayed by the method of Arthur and Boyne ^[4] as contained in Randox kit. Catalase activity was assayed with the randox kit according to the method described by Sinha ^[5]. Glutathione peroxidase (GPx) was measured according to the method of Paglia and Valentine ^[6], while the reduced glutathione level was determined by the method of Exner et al. ^[7].

Hematological Evaluations

The total white blood cell count was determined by haemocytometry following the method described by Ochei and Kolhatkar ^[8]. The method of Ochei and Kolhatkar (2008) ^[8] was used for the determination of red blood cells, where, the blood specimen was diluted 1:200 with RBC diluting fluid and cells were counted under high power (40×) objective by using a counting chamber. The number of cells was calculated and reported as the number of red cells/mm³ of whole blood. The packed cell volume was determined using the microhaematocrit centrifuge (JouanA13 model). The haemoglobin (Hb) concentration was measured spectrophotometrically by cyanomethaemoglobin method. The platelet count was obtained using the haemocytometer.

Data Analysis and Statistical Procedures

Statistical analysis of the data was carried out with SPSS version 22.0 using One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The statistically analyzed data were reported as Mean \pm SD. Significant difference was accepted at 95% confidence level of probability i.e. if $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Effects of Consumption on Haematological Parameters

	WBC(x10 ⁹ /L)	RBC(x10 ¹² /L)	PLATELET(x10 ⁹ /L)	PCV (%)	HB (g/dL)
Control	4.15	3.09	9	36.75	13.15
Group 1	5.23	3.41	219	42.23	16.21
Group 2	4.09	3.14	243.51	38.19	11.92

Table 2: Group mean values Effect on haematological parameters of Wistar rats at week 4

	GPX	CAT	MDA	GSH
control	27.21	2.29	3.34	2.24
Group 1	48.22	4.12	4.02	3.42
Group 2	34.21	2.34	3.29	2.56

Induced stress on some biochemical parameters of Wistar rats at week 4

Groups with different subscripts are significant (p<0.05) when compared with the control

Key:

Group 0: Control

Group 1a: Noise exposure at 85 decibels

Group 1b: Noise exposure at 95 decibels

Group 1c: Noise exposure at 105 decibels

Group 1d: Noise exposure to at above 105 decibels

Group 2a: Noise exposure to at 55 decibels

Group 2b: Noise exposure to at 50 decibels

Group 2c: Noise exposure to at 45 decibels

Group 2d: Noise exposure to at 40 decibels

Group 2e: Noise exposure to at below 40 decibels

Table 3: Effect of noise induced stress on haematological parameters of Wistar rats at week 4

DISCUSSION

In this study the effects of generator noise pollution from a running noisy generator set on certain biochemical parameters were evaluated using wistar albino rats kept at different positions which is dependent on the measured sound level. The effects of noise pollution at these different sound pressure levels were considered and compared to the control group. This was achieved in two different groups of the animal exposure, in order to know the effects of our parameters at this distinguished sound pressure levels in group one and group two. Noise exposure higher than 90 dB is considered a source of stress (Wright *et al.*, 2014).

Oxidative stress is a state where there is a significant imbalance between oxidants and antioxidants which can cause cellular damage, dysfunction or death (Gouin *et al.*, 2012). The body produces more antioxidants that can help cushion the increasing oxidative stress ^[9]. The glutathione concentration of the Wistar rats in group1 exposed to high noise level (between 85db-105db) increased significantly ($p<0.05$) when compared to the control. Glutathione is a tripeptide that is found in many mammalian tissues and is a very necessary free-radical scavenger ^[10]. Glutathione plays a crucial role in the antioxidant defense system; removing free-radical species, such as hydrogen peroxide and superoxide radicals as well as maintaining membrane protein thiols. The significant increased level of the glutathione shows the body response to cushion the oxidative stress caused by the high noise. However the glutathione concentration of group2 exposed to low noise level (between 55db-40db) increased significantly but not as high as those in group one which obviously shows that the oxidative stress at that sound pressure isn't much.

Lipid peroxidation is an oxidative process where reactive oxygen species and free radicals generated break down lipid molecules, especially the lipids on the cell membrane leading to cell death. Malondialdehyde is one of the byproducts of lipid peroxidation and a good indicator of oxidative stress. The result of our study showed that malondialdehyde concentration of the wistar rats in group1 exposed to high noise level (between 85db-105db) increased significantly ($p<0.05$) when compared to the control. This indicates that the noise stress at that sound pressure level caused an increased oxidation stress. This result agrees with the result from many studies done on noise effects on lipid peroxidation.

The antioxidative enzyme glutathione peroxidase, catalyzes the conversion of Hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) to water (H_2O) by using reduced glutathione (GSH) and reduced NADPH as cofactors (Molina *et al.*, 2016). Glutathione peroxidase is a major antioxidative enzyme in many tissues and has been speculated to be a major antioxidative

mechanism in the brain. Also in the antioxidant system, catalase catalyses two important reactions, firstly it catalyses the conversion of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) to water and oxygen, also secondly it catalyses the reduction of hydrogen and lipid peroxides which is also an oxidative defense function. This study agrees with other works done in effects of high sound pressure on the antioxidant enzymes. There was a significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in the activities of the antioxidant enzymes catalase and glutathione peroxidase in group1 exposed to high noise level (between 85db-105db) when compared with the control and group2, which indicates the action of the antioxidant enzymes in mopping up the generated free radicals, hence cushioning the oxidative stress that is produced from the increased lipid peroxidation and other oxidative mechanisms. The group2 exposed to low noise level (between 55db-40db) showed a significant ($p > 0.05$) decrease when compared with the group1, this reduced activity of the antioxidant enzymes shows a reduced oxidation stress. The activity of the antioxidant enzymes builds up when there is increasing oxidation stress, as a way to cushion the effect of the increasing oxidative stress. The increased level of malondialdehyde and the concomitant increase in glutathione, glutathione peroxidase and the catalase enzyme shows the organism strive to adaptation in the environment.

Haematological assay suggests the physiological disposition of the Wistar rats. Haematological studies show the physiological responses of an animal to its internal environment Haematological parameters like red blood cell, white blood cell, packed cell volume, hemoglobin etc have been identified as a good indicator of the immune status of the animal. The results of this study are in accordance with past studies. The hematological parameters of the blood sample from the Wistar rats which include their red blood cell count, white blood cell count, platelets concentration, hemoglobin concentration and packed cell volume in group1 exposed to high noise level (between 85db-105db) increased significantly ($p < 0.05$) when compared to the control. This result agrees with the work done by Sabahi and colleagues which they discovered that the number of red blood cells, white blood cells, hemoglobin, and hematocrit of blood cells of mice increases due to noise exposure over time, which is caused due to effects of vibrating sound on the immune system and hence increasing blood parameters. Also Litman in his work explained that noise pollution can increase hemoglobin, hematocrit, and red blood cell count in oil refinery workers, while the mechanism of this process remained unclear ^[11]. Also hematological parameter like red blood cell, platelete and packed cell volume of the Wistar rats in group 2 exposed to low noise level (between 55db-40db) increased slightly though significantly ($p < 0.05$) above the control group but not as much as those in group 1 which shows that the noise level at that sound pressure is not a strong stressor to affect the immune system.

CONCLUSION

This current study suggested that chronic noise exposure from a running generator set could adversely affect the studied parameters in the Wistar rats. Chronic noise exposure can lead to depressed organism immunity to pathogens and other xenobiotics. Therefore, individuals who are closely exposed to noisy generator set during their work period may be victims of this health hazards. The findings of this study have proved the importance of sensitizing the general public on the adverse health implications of chronic exposure to noise, especially, to people who run generator sets very close to their working desk or living rooms, which endangers them more to this health hazards. Owing to these findings, health policy makers should sensitize the general public through health awareness programmes on the health consequences of their exposure to noisy generator set and also make recommendations on safety measures they should adopt to protect themselves from these exposures during work and in their living houses.

Further studies are required to assess the health consequences of individuals exposed to other sources of stress during work which will give a general guide to the stressors that cumulatively cause the health hazards.

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